

NUTRIENT UPTAKE *VIS A VIS* YIELD OF PUDDLED TRANSPLANTED RICE AS INFLUENCED BY NDVI VALUES OF GREEN SEEKER AND NITROGEN LEVELSSuresh Kumar Billa¹, Ramana Murthy K.V², Ramana A.V³ And Jagannadham J⁴¹Department of Agronomy, Agricultural College, Naira, Srikakulam-532185, Acharya NG Ranga Agricultural University, Andhra Pradesh sureshkumarcbm@gmail.com²Principal Scientist (Agronomy) & Head, Agricultural Research Station-Ragolu-532 484, Andhra Pradesh³Professor & Head, Department of Agronomy, Agricultural College, Naira-532 185, Andhra Pradesh⁴Senior Scientist, Department of Soil Science & Agricultural chemistry, Agricultural Research Station-Amadalavalasa-532 185, Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract

A field trial was conducted to find out the suitable NDVI value and optimum nitrogen level for North Coastal Andhra Pradesh on sandy loam soils of Agricultural College Farm, Naira, during kharif, 2018 with four NDVI values of green seeker in combination with four nitrogen levels. The results revealed that, nitrogen uptake at all stages except at active tillering stage was highest with the NDVI value 0.8 with elevated drymatter production and grain yield at 120 kg N ha⁻¹ and found significantly superior over rest of the NDVI values of green seeker and nitrogen levels.

Key words : NDVI, Nitrogen levels, Yield and N uptake

Introduction

Nitrogen (N) fertilizer is the key input in most rice soils to accomplish high yield. The current recommendations of split application of N fertilizer with fixed rates at specific growth stages for large rice growing area assume the requirement of rice for fertilizer is constant across large areas and years. The requirement of rice for N fertilizer can, however, vary greatly from location to location, season to season and year to year because of high variability among fields, seasons and years in N supplying capacity of soil (Cassman *et al.*, 1993). These 'blanket' recommendations have served their purpose in producing higher yields, but they are limited in their capacity to increase nutrient use efficiency. Many times, to ensure high yields, farmers apply fertilizer N rates even higher than the blanket recommendation. Over application of N in rice crop leads to further lowering of N fertilizer recovery efficiency. The optimum use of nitrogen can be achieved by matching N supply with crop demand (Bijay Singh *et al.*, 2002). Improving the synchrony between crop N demand and the N supply from soil and or the applied N fertilizer is likely to be the most practical strategy to increase N use efficiency. The chlorophyll or SPAD meter is inexpensive and simple alternative, the leaf color chart can quickly and reliably monitor relative greenness of leaf as an indicator of leaf N status (Bijay Singh *et al.*, 2011). These tools have helped in developing real time N management strategies for rice but do not take into account photosynthetic rates or the biomass production and expected yields for working out fertilizer N requirements (Ladha *et al.*, 2005). Recently, methods based on measurements of reflectance in the red (defined by chlorophyll content) and near infrared (defined by living vegetation) region of the electro-magnetic spectrum for estimating N requirement of crops using early season estimates of N uptake and potential yield have been developed. Measured spectral reflectance is expressed as spectral vegetation indices such as Normalized difference vegetative index (NDVI). Normalized difference vegetative index based on in-season sensor reading can predict biomass, plant N concentration and plant N uptake. Hence, the present investigation was therefore taken up with four NDVI values and four nitrogen levels.

Materials and Methods

Field experiment was undertaken at Agricultural College Farm, Naira to study the effect of NDVI values of green seeker and graded levels of nitrogen on nitrogen uptake and economics of transplanted rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) during kharif season, 2018. The mean maximum and minimum temperatures recorded during crop period were 32.7°C and 22.9°C respectively. A total rainfall of 541.3 mm was received during the crop period. The soil (0-30 cm) of the

experimental site was sandy loam in texture, slightly alkaline in reaction with pH 7.1, EC 0.072 dSm⁻¹ and low in organic carbon (0.35) and available nitrogen (240 kg ha⁻¹), medium in available phosphorus (53 kg ha⁻¹) and available potassium (220 kg ha⁻¹). The experiment was laid out in split plot design with three replications consisted of sixteen treatment combinations. Four NDVI values of green seeker such as 0.6 (M₁), 0.7 (M₂), 0.8 (M₃) and 0.9 (M₄) were grown in main plots and four graded levels of nitrogen such as N₁ - 60 kg ha⁻¹, N₂-80 kg ha⁻¹, N₃-100 kg ha⁻¹ and N₄-120 kg ha⁻¹ were grown in sub plots. Application of nutrients was done as per the treatments in the form of urea, single super phosphate and muriate of potash respectively. Basal application of 1/3rd N was done and the remaining 2/3rd N was top dressed as per green seeker readings. The NDVI values were indicated through green seeker. Spectral properties were measured at 10 days interval starting from 20 days after transplanting (DAT) till flowering stage. The green seeker instrument was hand held at distance of 60-120 cm against the crop canopy and random readings were recorded on pressing the trigger. Whenever these NDVI values fall below the threshold value as mentioned in the main treatments, nitrogen was top dressed immediately to meet the N requirement irrespective of the stage of the crop. The final split application of N was completed by 70 DAT coinciding with the flowering stage. Entire quantity of phosphorus and half dose of potassium was applied at the time of transplanting. Remaining dose of potassium were applied at PI stage of the crop. The plant samples of rice collected for chemical analysis at AT, PI, flowering and at harvest were ground in a Willey mill to pass through 40 mesh sieve. Nitrogen was estimated by Micro Kjeldahl's method (Jackson, 1973). The data obtained on different parameters were analysed statistically using Fisher's method of analysis of variance as suggested by Panse and Sukhatme (1985).

Results and Discussion**Effect of NDVI values of green seeker and nitrogen levels on grain and straw yield**

From the Table 1, highest grain and straw yield of rice was recorded with N applied at NDVI value 0.8 (M₃) but was comparable with NDVI value 0.7 (M₂) and both of them were significantly superior to the other NDVI values of green seeker studied. Among the graded levels of nitrogen application, the highest grain and straw yield of rice was recorded with application of nitrogen @ 120 kg ha⁻¹ (N₄), which was significantly superior over all the other levels of nitrogen.

Nitrogen application through NDVI values of green seeker ranging from 0.7 to 0.8 can be considered for achieving higher yield as they matched with crop N demand. This might also be due to higher

quantity of nitrogen applied in more number of splits compared to other levels. These results are also in close conformity with the findings of Maiti and Das (2006) who have reported higher grain yield with LCC based nitrogen management. Increase in yield components are associated with better nutrition, plant growth and increased nutrient uptake. It is well known that yield is a manifestation of the individual yield components and therefore in this case also the nitrogen dose which resulted in highest grain yield (120 kg N ha⁻¹) was due to the similar results with graded levels of nitrogen noticed by various researchers *viz.*, Ramana Murthy *et al.* (2012) and Kabat and Satapathy (2013). Better absorption of nutrients and their utilization in growth promotion, assimilation from the source to sink coupled with the steady and adequate supply of nitrogen at the required time might have resulted in increased production of straw. Application of higher dose of 'N' promoted more dry matter production resulting in significant increase in straw yield which is again attributed to highest LAI, tillers m⁻² and higher level of N uptake at panicle initiation stage. The results are in line with the findings of Ravi *et al.* (2007).

Effect of NDVI values of green seeker and nitrogen levels on 'N' uptake

Nitrogen uptake recorded at AT, PI, flowering and at harvest was statistically analyzed and furnished in Table 1. At active tillering stage, computation and analysis of the data pertaining to nitrogen uptake showed that application of nitrogen through green seeker with NDVI value 0.9 (M₄) recorded the highest nitrogen uptake of rice which was significantly superior to the other NDVI values of green seeker studied. It was followed by application of nitrogen with NDVI value 0.8 (M₃) which was significantly superior to NDVI value 0.7 (M₂) and NDVI value 0.6 (M₁). Significantly higher N uptake was noticed with N applied at NDVI value 0.7 (M₂) compared to NDVI value 0.6 (M₁), which recorded significantly lower nitrogen uptake.

At panicle initiation, analysis of the data pertaining to nitrogen uptake revealed that NDVI value 0.8 (M₃) recorded highest N uptake but was, on parity with NDVI value 0.7 (M₂) and both of them were significantly superior to other NDVI value 0.9 (M₄) and NDVI value 0.6 (M₁). The significantly lowest nitrogen uptake of rice was recorded with NDVI value 0.6 (M₁) among all the NDVI values taken for study. The trend remained same with respect to nitrogen uptake at flowering stage and at harvesting stage by both grain and straw with NDVI values of green seeker as noticed at panicle initiation.

At all stages of observations (AT, PI, flowering and at harvest with both grain and straw), with respect to nitrogen levels tested in rice, nitrogen uptake was significantly different with each level of

Table 1. Uptake of nitrogen (kg ha⁻¹) at different stages and yield of rice as influenced by NDVI values of green seeker and graded levels of nitrogen.

Treatments	Active tillering (kg ha ⁻¹)	Panicle initiation (kg ha ⁻¹)	Flowering (kg ha ⁻¹)	Harvesting		Grain yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (kg ha ⁻¹)
				Grain (kg ha ⁻¹)	Straw (kg ha ⁻¹)		
NDVI values of Green seeker							
M ₁ :0.6	20.45	40.24	47.99	38.76	20.01	3772	5235
M ₂ :0.7	23.96	47.86	66.85	53.90	29.41	5097	6339
M ₃ :0.8	27.62	50.67	70.33	57.70	32.02	5411	6541
M ₄ :0.9	31.31	43.32	54.92	46.31	25.26	4441	5826
SEm (±)	0.81	1.12	1.78	1.43	0.86	105.42	143.20
CD (P=0.05)	2.86	3.96	6.29	5.05	3.06	371.89	505.17
CV (%)	10.88	8.55	10.29	10.14	11.26	7.80	8.29
Nitrogen levels (kg ha⁻¹)							
N ₁ :60	19.83	34.53	45.73	39.27	22.44	3965	5278
N ₂ :80	23.09	39.28	55.20	46.29	25.10	4444	5753

nitrogen from 60 to 120 kg ha⁻¹. The results of data at all rice growth stages showed that nitrogen uptake at the highest nitrogen level of 120 kg N ha⁻¹ (N₄) was significantly superior as compared to all the other the levels of nitrogen levels tried. Nitrogen uptake at all growth stages obtained with the application of 100 kg ha⁻¹ (N₃) was the next best treatment. N uptake with 80 kg N ha⁻¹ (N₂) was significant superior to 60 kg ha⁻¹ (N₁) which recorded the lowest nitrogen uptake and was significantly inferior to among all the N levels taken for study.

Highest N uptake at all stages of observation were recorded with NDVI value 0.8 might be due to better timing (20 DAT, 40 DAT and 50-60 DAT) and splitting of fertilizer N applications during the season leading to the increase in uptake of N by the crop which resulted inturn enhanced dry matter production and lead to higher N accumulation in plant. Maximum use of applied fertilizer N can be achieved with its synchrony to crop N demand. Nitrogen uptake was more at higher rate of nitrogen due to increased nitrogen content in plant tissue and crop yield probably because of adequate nitrogen available to plant for vegetative and reproductive growth as reported by Reena *et al.* (2017). Higher N uptake by grain might be due to more N availability and better translocation of available N ultimately resulted into more grain yield and higher N concentration in grain. Uptake of nitrogen increased because it was utilized for metabolism of various substances required for the growth of plants which produced more dry matter. The results are also in conformity with the findings of Gill and Aulakh (2018). The increase in nitrogen content in the straw might be due the increased available nitrogen status in the soil and increased availability of plant nutrients to the crop. The beneficial effect of better N management practices on N uptake might be attributed to their faster release of N during mineralization there by resulting in to higher N uptake by straw. The same observations were made by Pattanaik Ipista (2018).

These results indicate that the current recommendation of fixed-time split N applications at specified growth time are not adequate to synchronize N supply with actual crop N demand due to poorly designed N splitting and variations in crop N demand. Similar findings were also reported by Tauseef Bhat *et al.* (2014).

There was no interaction between NDVI values and nitrogen levels for all parameters studied. Green seeker based nitrogen application enhanced productivity and profitability of transplanted rice. Grain yield of 5411 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained with nitrogen application of 120 kg N ha⁻¹ based on NDVI threshold value 0.8. It is concluded that the Green seeker based N applications promises field efficient and effective technology to increase uptake of nitrogen, rice yield and net return for farmers in North Coastal Zone of Andhra Pradesh.

N ₃ :100	27.80	49.40	66.38	52.24	28.00	4912	6205
N ₄ :120	32.63	58.89	72.79	58.87	31.17	5400	6707
SEm (±)	0.55	1.12	1.82	1.50	0.63	131.32	144.53
CD (P=0.05)	1.62	3.30	5.35	4.42	1.85	385.58	424.36
CV (%)	7.39	8.56	10.53	10.62	8.22	9.72	8.36
Interaction							
SEm (±)	1.62	2.24	3.56	2.86	1.73	210.84	286.40
CD (P=0.05)	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

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